

Conductometric and Viscometric Studies of Gadolinium Soaps

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The most striking feature of metal soaps is their increasing importance in various industries. The studies of lanthanide and actinide soaps have not been carried out systematically so far, and only a few references are available in this field¹. The present work has been initiated with a view to study the micellar behaviour of gadolinium soaps, evaluate the various thermodynamic parameters and test the validity of well known equations.

Results and Discussion

Conductivity : The plot of specific conductance vs soap concentration indicates the formation of ionic micelles at this soap concentration. The intersections of the plots of n vs C and η_{sp} vs C show that the CMC decreases with increasing temperature and chainlength of fatty acid constituents of the soap (Table 1).

The dissociation constant, (K) for the soaps in pre-micellar region can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{[\text{Gd}^{3+}][\text{RCOO}^-]^3}{[\text{Gd}(\text{RCOO})_3]} = \frac{27C^3\alpha^4}{(1-\alpha)} \quad (1)$$

The activity coefficients of the ions have been assumed to be small at low concentration of electrolyte ($< 0.006 M$), C and α ($= \mu/\mu_0$) are the concentration and degree of dissociation of soap. On rearranging, equation (1) can be expressed as

$$\mu^3 C^3 = \frac{K\mu_0^4}{27\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^3}{27} \quad (2)$$

The value of μ_0 increases with increasing tem-

perature and chainlength of fatty acids while K decreases with increase in temperature (Table 1).

TABLE I—VALUES OF CMC, μ_0 AND K OF THE SOLUTIONS OF GADOLINIUM SOAPS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Sl no	Soap	Temp °C	$\times 10^{-3}$ CMC mol dm ⁻³	μ_0	$\times 10^{-7} K$
1	Caprate	30	6.4	0.68	12.4
		40	5.9	0.91	6.3
		50	5.3	1.43	3.5
2	Laurate	30	6.1	0.59	13.1
		40	5.5	0.67	6.7
		50	4.7	1.25	3.8
3	Myristate	30	5.7	0.90	11.8
		40	4.7	1.11	7.8
		50	4.4	1.33	6.6
4	Stearate	30	5.4	2.27	3.4
		40	4.5	2.65	2.4
		50	3.7	3.63	1.8

Thermodynamic parameters for dissociation and micellisation. *Dissociation process* : The values of heat of dissociation (ΔH_D^0) have been obtained from the slope of the linear plots of $\log K_D$ vs $1/T$ and are found to be -49.2 , -45.2 , 27.3 and -24.3 kJ mol⁻¹ for caprate, laurate, myristate and stearate respectively. The negative values of ΔH_D^0 indicate that the dissociation process is exothermic in nature. The other thermodynamic parameters (i.e. ΔG_D^0 and ΔS_D^0) are obtained from the relationship,

$$\Delta G_D^0 = -2.303 RT \log K_D = \Delta H_D^0 - T\Delta S_D^0$$

Association process : The free energy for micelle formation for ionic surfactants, ΔG_A^0 can be expressed

by the equations according to the phase separation approach to the micelle formation²,

$$\Delta G_A^0 = 2RT \ln X_{CMC} = \Delta H_A^0 - T\Delta S_A^0$$

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF GADOLINIUM SOAPS FOR DISSOCIATION AND ASSOCIATION PROCESS

Soap	ΔG_D^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	$\times 10^2 \Delta S_D^0$ kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG_A^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	$\times 10^2 \Delta S_A^0$ kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Caprate	37.16	-27.60	-40.87	17.21
Laurate	37.00	-26.28	-41.23	19.40
Myristate	36.56	-20.41	-42.05	20.77
Stearate	39.58	-20.42	-42.27	22.78

(assuming that the micellar phase is composed of the charged aggregate with an equivalent number of counter ions), where CMC is expressed in mole fraction unit and other symbols have their usual meanings. The values of ΔH_A^0 have been obtained from the slope of the linear plots of the $\log X_{CMC}$ vs $1/T$ and are recorded in Table 2. The results of thermodynamic parameters (negative values of ΔG_A^0 and positive values of ΔG_D^0 and negative values of ΔS_D^0 for dissociation process) indicate that the micellisation is favoured over dissociation process.

of the plots of Vand's equation⁴ ($1/C$ vs $1/\log(\eta/\eta_0)$) are in close agreement with the values obtained from Einstein equation. The plots of η_{sp}/C vs C below the CMC, have been extrapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated values (i.e. the intrinsic viscosity, η_i) increase with increasing chainlength of the soap molecules (Table 3).

The values of constant B (solute-solvent interaction) of Jones-Dole's⁵ equation are larger than those of constant A (solute-solute interaction) (Table 3). The values of Moulik's constants⁶ M and K (Table 3) obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots of $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 increase with increasing chainlength of fatty acid constituents of soap molecules.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Gadolinium soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap with slight excess of aqueous solution of gadolinium acetate at 50–55°. The purity of the soaps was checked by the determination of melting points of the soaps

TABLE 3—VALUES OF CMC, MOLAR VOLUME (\bar{V}), INTERACTION COEFFICIENT (ϕ), INTRINSIC VISCOSITY (η_i), CONSTANTS M AND K (FROM MOULIK'S EQUATION), A AND B (FROM JONES-DOLE'S EQUATION) AND VISCOSITY (η) FROM THE EXTRAPOLATION OF PLOTS AND FROM SOLVENT MIXTURE

Soap	$\times 10^{-3}$ CMC dm ⁻³	\bar{V} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)		ϕ	η_i	M	K $\times 10^{-3}$	A	B	η (cp)	
		Einstein eqn	Vand eqn							Solvent mixture	From extrapolation of plot
Caprate	6.4	7.55	7.68	-15.23	17.80	1.06	5.0	-0.04	20.0	0.4424	0.4420
Laurate	6.1	7.20	8.36	-14.35	19.60	1.08	5.0	0.07	18.0	0.4424	0.4430
Myristate	5.7	7.56	9.54	-15.72	23.90	1.08	5.8	0.15	19.13	0.4424	0.4440
Stearate	5.4	8.00	13.80	-15.97	30.60	1.07	8.1	0.57	16.36	0.4424	0.4490

Viscosity : The viscosity (η) and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) of the solutions of gadolinium soaps increase with increasing soap concentration and temperature. The plots of η_{sp} vs C are linear below the CMC with intercepts almost equal to zero, which shows that the Einstein equation³ is applicable to these solutions. The values of the molar volume (\bar{V}) of the soaps (Table 3) obtained from the slopes

(caprate, 98°; laurate, 102°; myristate, 108°; stearate, 115°). The absence of hydroxyl groups in these soaps was confirmed by ir spectra.

A Toshniwal C01.10A conductivity meter and a dip type conductivity cell were used for measuring the conductance of the soap solutions at different temperatures (30, 40 and 50 ± 0.05°).

References

1. K. N. MEHROTRA, A. S. GAHLAUT and M. SHARMA. *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 1571; *J. Colloid. Interface Sci.*, 1987, **120**, 110; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 103, 285, 331; R. P. VARMA and R. JINDAL, *Tenside Detergents*, 1983, **20**, 193; F. MAIN, D. MILLS and B. W. WHITE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, **67**, 172, 55355; B. LORANT, *Seifen-ole-Fette-Wachse*, 1967, **93**, 547; A. M. BHANDARI, S. DUBEY and R. N. KAPOOR, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **4**, 47; A. K. SOLANKI and A. M. BHANDARI, *Tenside Detergents*, 1981, **18**, 34; R. C. MEHROTRA, L. WISS Z. FRIEDRICH-SCHILLER, *Naturwiss.*, 1965, **14**, 171; S. N. MISRA, T. N. MISRA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 195, 201; K. N. MEHROTRA, R. K. SHUKLA and M. CHAUHAN, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1990, **39**, 1745; K. N. MEHROTRA and S. K. UPADHYAYA, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1989, **38**, 9.
2. D. ATTWOOD and A. T. FLORENCE, "Surfactant Systems", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1983, p.100.
3. A. EINSTEIN, *Ann. Phys.*, 1911, **34**, 501.
4. V. VAND, *J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 277.
5. G. JONES and M. DOLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
6. S. P. MOULIK. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4682.

